

A Comprehensive Review of Current Trends and Regulatory Frameworks in Generic Drug Development

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) are a global health concern, yet the role of non-clinical staff, particularly Harijan sweepers, remains underexplored. These workers face daily exposure to infection risks, unsafe waste handling, and inadequate protective measures. **Objectives:** To evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of Harijan sweepers at Rajshahi Medical College Hospital (RMCH), Bangladesh, regarding HAIs, waste management, and occupational safety. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 110 Harijan sweepers at RMCH (January–March 2024). Data were collected using a structured Bengali questionnaire and an observational checklist. Descriptive statistics, ANOVA, Pearson's correlation, and odds ratios (95% CI) were analysed using SPSS v24. **Results:** The participants were predominantly Hindus (92.73%) and female (64.6%) and ranged in age from 41 to 60 years (61.8%). Knowledge was moderate in 60.9%, poor in 27.3%, and good in 11.8%. Attitudes were moderate in 64.6%, but practices were poor in 61.8%. Only 2.7% segregated waste correctly, 17.3% used puncture-resistant sharps containers, and 16.4% disinfected PPE. More than half (52.7%) reported needle-stick injuries. KAP domains were positively correlated ($r = 0.327-0.612$) but not statistically significant. **Conclusion:** Harijan sweepers demonstrated moderate knowledge and attitudes but poor infection control practices. Interventions, including training, PPE provision, supervision, and safer waste systems, are urgently needed to protect cleaners and reduce HAIs.

Keywords: Generic drug development, Quality by Design, Process Analytical Technology, Regulatory framework..

INTRODUCTION

Generic drug products are pharmaceutical equivalent and alternative to innovator drug products, developed to match the reference product in terms of active pharmaceutical ingredient, dosage form, strength, route of administration, safety, efficacy, and therapeutic use [1]. Their development is a scientifically driven process that focuses on demonstrating bioequivalence ensuring that the rate and extent of drug absorption are not significantly different from the innovator product under similar conditions. Unlike innovator drug development, which undergo extensive preclinical and clinical testing, generic products rely on the established safety and efficacy profile of the reference product. This significantly reduces the time and cost associated with development. However, generic formulation is not without challenges it requires strict adherence to

regulatory standards, precise control of critical quality attributes, and the ability to replicate therapeutic performance without access to proprietary data from the original manufacturer [2, 3].

The increase in use of generic medicines has had a profound impact on global healthcare systems by improving affordability, accessibility, and treatment coverage, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Their cost-effectiveness stems from the absence of early-stage research and development expenses, as well as reduced marketing investments [4]. Furthermore, the availability of generics fosters market competition, which drives down drug prices and incentivizes innovation in both brand and generic sectors. Many generic products are developed following patent expiry or exclusivity loss of the innovator drug. During this transition, manufacturers must meet stringent regulatory expectations,

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including bioequivalence studies, robust quality assurance systems, and compliance with pharmacopeial standards. In recent years, the adoption of advanced development strategies such as Quality by Design [QbD], continuous manufacturing and Process Analytical Technology (PAT) has enhanced the precision, efficiency, and reliability of generic drug development and evaluation [5,6].

This review aims to provide a detailed overview of the current scientific approaches and evolving regulatory frameworks governing generic drug development. It also discusses emerging technologies, challenges, and strategic considerations that shape the development and approval process in today's highly regulated pharmaceutical environment.

THE HATCH-WAXMAN ACT AND ITS IMPACT ON GENERIC DRUG DEVELOPMENT

The **Drug Price Competition and Patent Term Restoration Act of 1984**, commonly known as the **Hatch-Waxman Act**, is a landmark in U.S. legislation that established a structured framework to balance pharmaceutical innovation with the promotion of affordable generic medicines. This act significantly reshaped the regulatory and patent landscape, enabling faster entry of generics into the market while preserving incentives for brand-name drug development. Under the Hatch-Waxman framework, **innovator companies** are allowed to recover research and development investments through **patent term extensions**, while **generic manufacturers** benefit from a simplified regulatory pathway via the **Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA)** process. ANDA applicants are not required to replicate full clinical trials but must demonstrate **bioequivalence** to the reference listed drug (RLD), ensuring similar safety, efficacy, and pharmacokinetic profiles [4,7]. Development and regulatory submission similarities and differences between NDA and ANDA application as per Hatch-Waxman act are tabulated in **Table 1**.

Key provisions of the Act include:

- **Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA):** Enables generic drug makers to rely on existing safety and efficacy data of the innovator product, provided bioequivalence is demonstrated.
- **Patent Certification and Orange Book Listings:** Generic applicants must certify one of four patent statuses (Paragraph I–IV) regarding patents listed in the FDA's Orange Book. Paragraph I - patent information relating to such patents has not been filed; Paragraph II - patents got expired; Paragraph III - patents will expire on a particular date; Paragraph IV - Patent Challenging.
- **Paragraph IV Certification:** Allows generics to challenge patents they believe are invalid or not infringed. If challenged, the innovator company can initiate a lawsuit within 45 days, triggering a **30-month stay** on generic approval while the dispute is resolved.
- **180-Day Exclusivity:** Granted to the **first generic filer** who successfully files a Paragraph IV challenge, this exclusivity period provides a temporary market monopoly among generics as a reward for challenging weak or invalid patents.
- **Patent Term Restoration:** Innovators can receive up to **five years of additional patent protection** to compensate for regulatory review delays, ensuring a fair period of market exclusivity.

The FDA plays a central role by **reviewing NDAs and ANDAs**, maintaining the Orange Book, and ensuring that all approved products meet stringent **quality, safety, and bioequivalence standards** [7].

The Hatch-Waxman Act not only expedited the availability of generic drugs, reducing healthcare costs, but also provided clear legal and regulatory pathways for resolving patent disputes. Its mechanisms particularly Paragraph IV certifications and the 180-day exclusivity remain central to the U.S. generic drug industry and continue to shape competitive strategies for both innovator and generic manufacturers.

Table 1: Differences and similarities between new drug application and Abbreviated New Drug Application as per the Hatch-Waxman Act

Aspect	NDA (New Drug Application)	ANDA (Abbreviated New Drug Application)	Para IV Filing
Purpose	Approval of a new, original drug.	To provide a lower-cost alternative to innovator drugs.	Challenge brand drug patents
Type	Regulatory submission for a new chemical entity (NCE) or drug.	Regulatory submission for a generic drug.	ANDA with Paragraph IV certification
Regulatory Pathway	Submission through 505(b)(1) - Full NDA with original data (safety, efficacy). 505(b)(2) - NDA relying partly on existing data (e.g., literature, previous approvals)	505(j)- Used for generics with stability and bioequivalence	ANDA + Para IV Certification
Clinical Trials	Required (Phases I–III for safety and efficacy).	Not required (only bioequivalence studies).	No (bioequivalence + legal challenge)
Data Submitted	Full preclinical, clinical, CMC, safety, and efficacy.	Bioequivalence, CMC, and labelling; no clinical efficacy data.	Same as ANDA + patent challenge justification
Approval Time	Longer (due to extensive data requirements).	Shorter (due to reduced data requirements).	Variable (often 30+ months due to patent litigation)
Innovation Level	High – includes new drugs and indications.	No innovation – same as approved reference drug.	Low – challenges IP but not therapeutic innovation
Cost to Develop	Very high (may up to billions).	Low (development cost recouped via high-volume sales).	Low (development cost recouped via high-volume sales).
Patent Protection	Yes – usually has patent and exclusivity periods.	Filed after patent/exclusivity of branded drug expires.	No (but challenges patent of RLD)
Regulatory Body	FDA, EMA, HC, PMDA, CDSCO, etc.	FDA, EMA, HC, PMDA, CDSCO, etc.	FDA (OGD) + Legal system (for litigation)
Time to Market	Long (most of the cases 10+ years)	Shorter (2–3 years)	3–7 years (includes litigation delay)
Paragraph Certifications	Not applicable	Must certify under Paragraph I–IV	Paragraph IV (claims patent invalidation)
Market Exclusivity	5 years (NCE), 3 years (new use)	None unless first-to-file benefit	Yes – 180 days (if first filer wins challenge)
Review Time (Est.)	10 – 12 months	8 – 10 months	Depends on litigation and review

QUALITY BY DESIGN (QBD) IN GENERIC DRUG DEVELOPMENT: INDUSTRIAL PRACTICES

QbD is a systematic, science and risk-based approach to pharmaceutical development that aims to ensure product quality through a deep understanding of formulation and manufacturing processes. Introduced

formally in pharmaceutical regulation through the FDA's twenty-first century cGMP initiative and ICH guidelines (Q8–Q11), QbD has become integral to modern **generic drug development**, enhancing product robustness, regulatory compliance, and manufacturing efficiency.

In generic drug development, QbD is used to define a **Quality Target Product Profile (QTPP)**, identify **Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs)** and **Critical Material Attributes (CMAs)**, and to control **Critical Process Parameters (CPPs)** to ensure consistent product quality and performance throughout the product lifecycle^[8,9]. Tools such as **risk assessment**, **Design of Experiments (DoE)**, **mechanistic modelling**, and **Process Analytical Technology (PAT)** are employed to facilitate knowledge-based development and real-time process control. Since **2013**, the U.S. FDA has mandated inclusion of QbD elements in **Abbreviated New Drug Applications**, making it a regulatory requirement for generic manufacturers. The FDA has provided QbD examples for immediate- and modified-release products, supporting industry adoption^[10,11,12,13].

Key industrial QbD practices include:

- **Establishing QTPP based on therapeutic goals, route of administration, dosage form, and patient needs.**
- **Defining CQAs, which are measurable attributes (Assay, Dissolution, moisture content, Content uniformity, Related substances) linked to product performance.**

- **Conducting Risk assessments (FMEA, HACCP) to prioritize variables impacting product quality.**
- **Utilizing Design of Experiments to optimize formulation and process parameters.**
- **Implementing PAT tools for real-time monitoring and control during manufacturing.**
- **Developing a control strategy to maintain process consistency and product quality.**
- **Applying lifecycle management principles for continuous process verification (CPV) and ongoing improvement post-approval.**

In industrial settings, QbD enhances formulation understanding, reduces variability, improves scalability, and facilitates faster regulatory approvals. Its adoption supports efficient technology transfer, robust manufacturing, and cost-effective production key objectives in generic drug development where time-to-market and compliance are critical^[14,15]. The comparative generic product development between conventional and QbD based approach are tabulated in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Comparison of Conventional vs. QbD Approach in Generic Drug Development

Development Stage	Conventional Approach	Quality by Design (QbD) Approach
Development Philosophy	Empirical and trial-and-error-based	Science, knowledge, and risk-based systematic approach
Objective Definition	Not clearly defined; objectives evolve during development	Defined early as QTPP based on patient and clinical needs
Process & Product Understanding	Limited understanding; gained post-development	Extensive understanding of product and process from early development stages
Risk Assessment / Management	Minimal or reactive	Proactive risk assessment (FMEA, FTA, HACCP) conducted at multiple stages
Design of Experiments	Often not used; relies on one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) experiments	DoE used to study multivariate effects and optimize formulation/process
Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs)	Identified late or during validation	Identified early; derived from QTPP and refined throughout development
Critical Material Attributes (CMAs)	Rarely defined explicitly	CMAs identified and controlled based on risk to CQAs
Critical Process Parameters (CPPs)	Determined post-hoc or during scale-up	Identified early; controlled to maintain CQAs and ensure robustness
Process Optimization	Performed post-development or during scale-up	Embedded in development using statistical and mechanistic tools

Development Stage	Conventional Approach	Quality by Design (QbD) Approach
Control Strategy	Relies heavily on final product testing	Focuses on in-process controls and real-time release testing (PAT integration)
Technology Transfer	Challenging due to lack of process understanding	Easier and more robust due to detailed process knowledge and defined design space
Regulatory Submissions	Based on limited process understanding and final product specs	Includes scientific rationale, risk assessments, and a well-defined design space
Process Validation	One-time event -Three-batch validation	Lifecycle approach including Continued Process Verification (CPV)
Change Management	Changes often require full revalidation	Within a defined design space, many changes can be managed without regulatory resubmission
Product Life-cycle Management	Reactive changes; post-approval issues handled as they arise	Proactive lifecycle management with emphasis on continuous improvement
Regulatory Compliance	Compliance-focused; quality by inspection	Quality is built into the product; facilitates easier regulatory approvals
Time and Cost Efficiency	Longer development time; higher cost due to inefficiencies and late-stage failures	Reduced development time and cost through proactive design and fewer post-approval issues

Comparative bioequivalence studies are a critical requirement, demonstrating that the generic product delivers the same amount of active ingredient into a patient's bloodstream in the same time frame as the innovator product. By integrating QbD principles such as defining a Quality Target Product Profile, identifying CQAs, and using risk-based approaches

generic product developers can efficiently design robust formulations and processes that meet regulatory expectations for BE, ensuring safety, efficacy, and quality in generic medicines. The comparative BE requirements and acceptance criteria among the different regulatory agencies are tabulated in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Comparative BE requirements and acceptance criteria between different regulatory agencies

Agency	General Acceptance Range (Solid Oral Dosage Forms, Immediate-Release)	Criteria for Narrow Therapeutic Index (NTI)	Highly Variable Drugs (HVD)	Fasted vs Fed / Special Conditions	Other Remarks / Unique Aspects
FDA (USA)	90% CI for test/reference geometric mean ratio of AUC and C_{max} must lie within 80.00–125.00 %.	For NTI drugs: tighter limits via reference-scaled average bioequivalence; often around 90.00-111.11 % for AUC (and sometimes C_{max}) depending on variability of reference product. Design often requires fully replicated crossover.	FDA allows scaled bioequivalence approaches for HVDs, particularly for C_{max} ; limits may be widened based on within-subject variability of reference product.	Generally, fasted studies are standard; fed studies required in many cases (especially modified / extended release / food effect) and also for NTI where relevant.	FDA provides product-specific guidance; classification of NTI drugs is product-by-product; sponsors often consult FDA guidance to see if a drug is classified NTI.

Agency	General Acceptance Range (Solid Oral Dosage Forms, Immediate-Release)	Criteria for Narrow Therapeutic Index (NTI)	Highly Variable Drugs (HVD)	Fasted vs Fed / Special Conditions	Other Remarks / Unique Aspects
EMA (Europe)	Same standard: 90% CI of AUC and C_{max} within 80.00–125.00 %.	For NTI drugs: 90.00–111.11 % for AUC; C_{max} tighter only if its variation significantly affects safety or therapeutic effect.	EMA may allow wider C_{max} criteria for highly variable drugs (e.g. widening beyond standard), but this is more restrictive for safety-critical parameters.	Fasted and fed studies often required, especially for extended release or modified release products. Regulatory guidance emphasizes food effect.	EMA's guideline update process (e.g., forthcoming ICH M13A) seeks further harmonization; NTI criteria assessed case-by-case by EMA PK Working Party.
PMDA (Japan)	Standard 80.00 – 125.00 % for AUC and C_{max} for solid oral IR products.	Japan guidelines recognize NTI (“Critical Dose”) drugs and may require tighter acceptance (e.g. 90-111 %) for some NTI drugs. Some sources show that PMDA expects both AUC and C_{max} criteria for NTI similar to others.	Less public data on formally scaled BE for HVD in Japan; often same standard unless variability is extreme. Japan does allow for certain special designs or requirements.	Fasted vs fed: for immediate release, often fasted; extended/modified release often require fed and fasted conditions. Also water volume and subject conditions are specified.	Japan requires development of marketed strengths for innovator; in BE studies dosage forms, comparison is required for all marketed strengths. Japanese reference product must be appropriate.
Health Canada (HC)	Standard acceptance: 80.00-125.00 % for both AUC and C_{max} in single-dose crossover studies for most generic / subsequent entry drugs.	For “critical dose drugs” (NTI equivalent): tighter acceptance for AUC (90.00-112.00 %); C_{max} usually maintained at 80-125%. Both fasted and fed states may be required.	Health Canada is implementing ICH M13A (to be effective Dec 27, 2025) which may revise BE standards especially for modified-release dosage forms.	For modified release, both fasted and fed study conditions are required. Also for drugs with long half-life or special absorption features.	Canada uses “Canadian Reference Product (CRP)” policy; proportional formulations may allow waivers for additional strengths if requirements are met. Also policy for using foreign comparator if criteria satisfied.
CDSCO (India)	Publicly: generic solid oral dosage forms must show BE but acceptance range specifics are based on national	There is less clarity / no widely published detailed guidance (in	Data on HVDs or expanded limits under Indian regulation is not	Conditions like fed vs fasted studies are required for modified-release formulations or	CDSCO follows ICH / WHO principles; India accepts biowaivers for certain BCS Class

Agency	General Acceptance Range (Solid Oral Dosage Forms, Immediate-Release)	Criteria for Narrow Therapeutic Index (NTI)	Highly Variable Drugs (HVD)	Fasted vs Fed / Special Conditions	Other Remarks / Unique Aspects
	guidance, commonly 80-125 % for rate and extent of absorption. (Though authoritative source absence for detailed NTI criterion found in search.)	public domain) about NTI-specific tighter acceptance criteria under CDSCO; for some drugs categories or certain drugs they may apply more stringent controls, but documentation is limited.	well-documented in public sources found.	as per guidance; in vivo BE studies must be conducted in humans.	1 drugs under conditions; studies must be done in Indian subjects typically.

PAT TOOLS IN PHARMACEUTICAL DEVELOPMENT

Process Analytical Technology is a cornerstone of the QbD paradigm, introduced by the U.S. FDA to facilitate the design, analysis, and control of pharmaceutical manufacturing through timely measurements of critical quality and performance attributes. PAT tools enable real-time, in-process monitoring of manufacturing operations, allowing for a deeper understanding of the relationships between formulation variables, process parameters, and product quality. These tools include spectroscopic techniques such as Near-Infrared (NIR), Raman, and UV-Vis spectroscopy, as well as chromatographic

methods, particle size analysers, and multivariate data analysis software. By implementing PAT, manufacturers can identify trends, detect deviations, and control variability in real time reducing batch failures, enhancing product consistency, and ensuring regulatory compliance. In the context of generic drug development, where cost efficiency and speed to market are critical, PAT supports robust process validation, continuous process verification, and ultimately facilitates faster regulatory approval. As the pharmaceutical industry advances toward continuous manufacturing, the integration of PAT tools (**Table 4**) becomes increasingly essential to achieve automation, real-time release testing (RTRT), and a truly science-driven manufacturing environment ^[15,16].

Table 4: Overview of PAT Tools in Pharmaceutical Manufacturing

PAT Tool	Mechanism	Common Applications	Stage of Manufacturing
Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (NIR)	Measures absorption of NIR light by molecular bonds (typically O-H, C-H, N-H)	Blend uniformity Moisture content API quantification	Blending Granulation Drying
Raman Spectroscopy	Measures inelastic scattering of light due to molecular vibrations	Raw material identification Polymorph detection Coating analysis	Raw material analysis Final product testing
Ultraviolet-Visible (UV-Vis) Spectroscopy	Measures light absorption in UV-Vis range	Dissolution profiling API content Assay	In-process testing Quality control

PAT Tool	Mechanism	Common Applications	Stage of Manufacturing
Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)	Measures IR absorption spectra for functional group identification	API/excipient compatibility Reaction monitoring	Pre-formulation Synthesis Characterization
Mass Spectrometry (MS)	Detects ions based on mass-to-charge ratio	Impurity profiling Degradation product identification	API synthesis Final testing
High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)	Separates compounds based on polarity and interaction with stationary phase	Assay of API and impurities Content uniformity	In-process QC Final product release
Laser Diffraction	Measures particle size distribution based on light scattering patterns	Granule and powder sizing Suspension and emulsion analysis	Milling Granulation
Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)	Measures Brownian motion of particles to estimate particle size	Nanoparticle and liposomal formulation analysis	Pre-formulation Emulsification
Focused Beam Reflectance Measurement (FBRM)	Measures chord length distribution via backscattered laser light	Particle size monitoring in suspensions or slurries	Crystallization Granulation
Process Gas Chromatography (GC)	Separates volatile compounds using gas-phase chromatography	Residual solvent analysis Headspace analysis	Drying Final product QC
X-ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD)	Identifies crystalline structure via diffraction pattern of X-rays	Polymorph identification Crystallinity assessment	Solid-state characterization API development
Thermal Analysis (e.g., DSC, TGA)	Measures changes in material properties with temperature (e.g., enthalpy, mass)	Stability studies Excipient compatibility	Pre-formulation Product optimization
Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT)	High-resolution imaging technique based on low-coherence interferometry	Real-time monitoring of film coating thickness and uniformity in tablet manufacturing.	Tablet and film coating
Multivariate Data Analysis (MVDA)	Analyzes complex data sets using statistical and chemometric tools	Process modelling Trend monitoring Outlier detection	Throughout development and manufacturing lifecycle

REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR GENERIC DRUG DEVELOPMENT

The regulatory framework governing generic drug development is robust yet adaptive, shaped by scientific advancement and emerging safety concerns to ensure the delivery of high-quality, safe, and effective medications. In the United States, the cornerstone of this system is the **Hatch-Waxman Act**, which established a streamlined pathway for the approval of generics through the **Abbreviated New Drug Application** process. This mechanism allows generic manufacturers to rely on the safety and

efficacy data of an already approved **Reference Listed Drug (RLD)**, provided they demonstrate **bioequivalence** in pharmacokinetic parameters. The **U.S. Food and Drug Administration** requires generic products to meet the same stringent standards of **identity, strength, quality, purity, and potency**, and mandates compliance with **Current Good Manufacturing Practices (cGMP)**.

In response to evolving challenges, the regulatory landscape has expanded to address specific concerns. For instance, the detection of **nitrosamine impurities**, which are classified as probable human carcinogens, has prompted the FDA and other global

regulatory agencies to implement risk-based assessment and control strategies in both active pharmaceutical ingredients and finished products. Similarly, the development of generics for **Narrow Therapeutic Index (NTI) drugs**, where small differences in dose or blood concentration may lead to serious therapeutic failures or adverse effects, requires tighter bioequivalence limits and rigorous control of manufacturing variability. Additionally, while **orphan drugs** intended for rare diseases are generally granted market exclusivity, the FDA provides pathways for generic competition once exclusivity expires, though these products often pose scientific and ethical challenges due to limited patient populations and data availability [17,18,19].

Furthermore, regulatory submissions must include detailed **analytical method validation**, **stability data**, and **risk assessments**, especially for products using complex delivery systems or involving advanced manufacturing technologies. Post-approval requirements such as **pharmacovigilance**, **post-marketing surveillance**, and **continued process verification** are integral to ensuring long-term safety and efficacy. Collectively, this evolving regulatory framework not only facilitates timely and cost-effective market entry of generics but also strengthens public trust by upholding high standards of pharmaceutical quality and patient safety. Comparative Regulatory Submission Requirements for Generic Drug Development Across Major Regulatory Agencies are tabulated in **Table 5**.

Table 5: Comparative regulatory submission requirements for generic drug product development across major regulatory agencies

Parameter	FDA (USA)	EMA (Europe)	CDSCO (India)	TGA (Australia)	PMDA (Japan)	Health Canada (HC)
Application Type	ANDA (Abbreviated New Drug Application)	Generic application (via centralized / national procedures)	Form 44 + CTD Dossier	CTD-based Generic Medicine Submission	GCTD or Partial Change Application	ANDS (Abbreviated New Drug Submission)
Reference Product	Reference Listed Drug (RLD)	EU Reference Product	Indian-marketed product or global RLD	Australian Reference Product (ARP)	Approved Japanese reference product	Canadian Reference Product (CRP)
BE Requirement	Mandatory unless BCS-based waiver applies	Mandatory unless BCS-based waiver applies	Mandatory for most dosage forms	Mandatory	Bioequivalence + comparative dissolution	Mandatory or justified waiver based on BCS
Therapeutic Equivalence Coding	Orange Book (AB rating)	No direct TE coding, but standards enforced	No formal system	Not applicable	Not applicable	No formal TE code; relies on BE & quality
Quality Standards	USP/NF or justified alternative	Ph. Eur. or justified alternative	IP/USP/Ph. Eur. accepted	BP/Ph. Eur./USP	JP (Japanese Pharmacopoeia)	USP/Ph. Eur. preferred
Labelling Requirements	Label must match RLD (except certain sections)	Must be in line with EU reference	Should match approved brand	Must be consistent with ARP	Language: Japanese only	English/French bilingual labelling mandatory

Parameter	FDA (USA)	EMA (Europe)	CDSCO (India)	TGA (Australia)	PMDA (Japan)	Health Canada (HC)
Patent / Exclusivity Considerations	Hatch-Waxman: Patent certification + 180-day exclusivity	Data exclusivity: 8+2(+1) years rule	Patent info optional; no exclusivity regime	No linkage between patent and registration	Patent not linked to approval	Data exclusivity: 6 years NDS, 8 years biologics
NTI Drug Requirements	Tighter BE limits (90–111%) for NTIs	EMA guideline for NTIs requires similar tightening	Handled case-by-case	Follows EMA-like guidance	Case-by-case + additional clinical data	NTI classification & tight BE required
Impurities / Nitrosamines	Risk-based assessment + control limits	Strict control per EMA & ICH M7	CDSCO follows WHO + ICH guidelines	Aligns with EMA & ICH	Follows ICH M7; recent alerts on nitrosamines	Health Canada guidance + ICH M7
Manufacturing Site Approval	CGMP inspection required before approval	EU-GMP inspection or Mutual Recognition	Site registered and periodically inspected	PIC/S member; GMP certificate required	Pre-approval inspection + GMP certificate	GMP compliance via on-site or foreign audit
Stability Requirements	ICH Q1A(R2); Zone II/IVB (climatic)	ICH Q1A(R2); Zone I/II/III depending on member state	ICH Q1A(R2); Zone IVB (India is hot/humid)	ICH Q1A(R2); Zone III	ICH Q1A(R2); Zone I	ICH Q1A(R2); Zone II
Regulatory Timelines (Avg.)	10–12 months (priority <8 months)	12–18 months	12–15 months	10–12 months	12–18 months	10–12 months

Regulatory Fees for Generic Drugs

The regulatory approval process for generic drugs involves various fees that support the review and oversight functions of national regulatory agencies. In the United States, the Generic Drug User Fee Amendments (GDUFA) first enacted in 2012 and reauthorized as GDUFA II (2017–2022) and GDUFA III (2023–2027) establish fee structures for Abbreviated New Drug Applications (ANDAs), Drug Master Files (DMFs), facilities, and annual program fees. These fees are designed to ensure timely review, enhance regulatory transparency, and improve communication between the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the generic pharmaceutical

industry. For example, the ANDA filing fee under GDUFA III is approximately \$240,000, while facility fees vary depending on whether the site is foreign or domestic, and whether it manufactures active pharmaceutical ingredients or finished dosage forms. Similar fee structures are imposed by other major regulatory authorities: the European Medicines Agency (EMA) charges fees based on centralized or decentralized submissions, while agencies like Health Canada, TGA (Australia), and PMDA (Japan) also apply submission, evaluation, and maintenance fees for generic drugs [20,21]. These regulatory fees contribute to the sustainability of regulatory systems but also add to the economic burden of generic drug development, especially for small and medium-sized manufacturers. As regulatory requirements become

more complex, the cost of compliance including user fees continues to be a critical consideration in strategic planning for global generic drug market entry.

Advances and Current Trends in Generic Drug Development

The landscape of generic drug development is undergoing a significant transformation driven by emerging technologies and patient-focused approaches. One of the most impactful innovations is **3D printing** or **additive manufacturing**, which enables the production of personalized dosage forms with tailored release profiles, shapes, and doses particularly beneficial for individualized therapy. Techniques such as **fused deposition modelling**, **semi-solid extrusion**, and **pressure-assisted microsyringe (PAM) printing** allow for the fabrication of complex oral solid formulations on demand. Simultaneously, **patient-centric formulation strategies** are gaining traction, especially for vulnerable populations like paediatrics and geriatrics. These include **orodispersible tablets and films**, **polyprintlets** (multi-drug printed dosage forms), and **palatability-enhanced formulations**, aimed at improving medication adherence and therapeutic outcomes. In parallel, **continuous manufacturing** supported by **Process Analytical Technology** is streamlining pharmaceutical production. PAT enables real-time monitoring and control of **CPPs** and **CMAs**, ensuring consistency, quality, and reduced process variability. The integration of **artificial intelligence (AI)** and **machine learning (ML)** further supports data-driven development by optimizing formulation design, predicting stability and dissolution profiles, and minimizing trial-and-error experimentation [22,23,24].

Regulatory authorities such as the **U.S. FDA**, **European Medicines Agency (EMA)**, **PDMA**, **CDSO** and **Health Canada** are progressively adapting to these innovations. The FDA's approval of **Spritam®**, the first 3D-printed drug, marks a pivotal step toward regulatory acceptance of such advanced manufacturing methods. Nonetheless, challenges remain, including the **validation and scalability** of novel technologies, the **stability of thermosensitive active ingredients**, **standardization of regulatory**

requirements, and maintaining **quality assurance** in decentralized or on-demand production environments. These advancements collectively signal a shift toward more agile, personalized, and technology-driven approaches in generic drug development.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES FOR GENERIC DRUG DEVELOPMENT

The future of generic drug development is poised to be shaped by the integration of cutting-edge technologies, evolving regulatory frameworks, and increasing global demand for affordable yet high-quality therapeutics. Advancements such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are expected to play a pivotal role in accelerating formulation optimization, bioequivalence prediction, and process design, thereby reducing development time and cost. Additive manufacturing (3D printing) holds promise for personalized medicine, allowing for patient-specific dosage forms and combination therapies, particularly beneficial for populations with unique therapeutic needs, such as paediatrics and geriatrics. Continuous manufacturing, coupled with real-time monitoring tools like Process Analytical Technology (PAT), is anticipated to enhance production efficiency, scalability, and quality assurance. Regulatory harmonization, particularly through initiatives like the International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) M13 guidelines for bioequivalence, will facilitate smoother global development and approval processes. Additionally, the increasing emphasis on sustainability and digital transformation is likely to drive innovations in packaging, supply chain logistics, and lifecycle management of generic products. Overall, the future of generic drug development is expected to be more patient-centric, technologically advanced, and globally aligned, ensuring broader access to safe, effective, and affordable medicines.

CONCLUSION

This current comprehensive review underscores the dynamic and multifaceted nature of generic drug development, highlighting its critical role in enhancing global access to affordable and effective medicines. The integration of QbD principles and advanced manufacturing technologies, such as

continuous manufacturing and Process Analytical Technology, is revolutionizing the industry by improving process understanding, ensuring consistent product quality, and facilitating regulatory compliance. The regulatory landscape, shaped by foundational legislation like the Hatch-Waxman Act and harmonized efforts across agencies including the FDA, EMA, CDSCO, TGA, HC, PDMA and others, continues to evolve in response to scientific advancements and patient needs. Despite ongoing challenges related to bioequivalence demonstration, product complexity, and regulatory diversity, the future of generic drug development is promising. Emerging trends such as personalized medicine through 3D printing, artificial intelligence-driven formulation optimization, and real-time quality monitoring position the industry toward more efficient, patient-centric, and globally aligned drug development. Continued innovation, coupled with robust regulatory frameworks, will be essential to sustain the growth and impact of generics in meeting healthcare demands worldwide.

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The authors declare no conflict of interest

ETHICS APPROVAL:

None to declare.

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